

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SISSAO****FIRST NAME: MOUMINE****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 02%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) :

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-14)
2. Rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 12-14)
3. American versus British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40-42)

COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)

1)INTRODUCTION

Through this open response paper, I would like to discuss and demonstrate my progress regarding five (5) points mentioned in the coursepack (EUCLID 2023). The response paper covers essay writing, America versus British English, plagiarism, a style guide, and sample of corrections to paper. This fourth edition of the period one coursepack provides international academic and professional paper writing basics. The first study material introduces students to academic writing at Euclid University (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3).

2)ESSAY WRITING

This point corresponds to chapter one of the coursepack (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-14). It is useful for having a general overview of the basics of essay writing, understanding the steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper. The emphasis is put on an academic essay which is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic writing include research findings or report

on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference papers; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above. Academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7).

Even if the steps for writing an academic essay are not rigidly linear, some basic steps need to be considered. They are researching the topic, organizing ideas, writing the Essay considering three parts (introduction, body, and conclusion), referencing the Essay since all academic essays must contain references, editing the essay, and handing the essay in. I retain some rules of thumb for writing a paper as follows: state the main thesis of your paper at (or near) the beginning, stay focused, do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) generalities, write clearly, do not make the writing boring and clumsy, support assertions, take the views you are discussing seriously, do not plagiarize.

3) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

As I am preparing a doctorate degree and since my dissertation will be in English, it is important to understand two types of English language used for writing (American and British English). The second point discussed is relevant for this purpose and to capture the differences between the two types of English.

American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English." The following general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) each have their sociolectic value (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25-32):

- Different pronunciation, although same spelling
- Different spelling, although same pronunciation
- Same term, different but similar spelling, and pronunciation
- Same words, but different or additional meanings
- Grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage
- Differences in usage with SBE 'large collective nouns'
- Differences in usage with SBE 'pluralized adjectives'

4) PLAGIARISM

This third discussed point corresponds to chapter four (4) of coursepack. As a doctorate student and future researcher, I am aware that it is necessary to know what plagiarism is, how to avoid it, to know how and when to cite and paraphrase, and to be able to insert footnotes using MS Word.

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. It is wrong and unethical; it is unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit, and it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34). To avoid plagiarism, I will give credit to the author when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or graph that is borrowed from another source, and cite properly the author or source that has provided the information I will use.

I can now distinguish in-text citations and a list of works cited. Commonly, the citation method uses quotations (the exact words of an author) and paraphrasing. Even if the quotations are interesting, I need to limit their use. I will use quotations when there is especially strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well, when an authority figure says something that can help you persuade (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34).

Paraphrases are the ideas and information an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words. In a paper, it does not look very good if you have too many quotes (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34). So I will need to paraphrase at times.

For citation and list of works cited, I will refer to Turabian 2008, 133, §18.3.1 for the rule of style.

5) STYLE GUIDE

This fourth discussed point is chapter five (5) of coursepack of period one (1). Through this, I have understood what a style guide is and why as a writer, I need a particular style guide.

"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

I have become familiar with Chicago rules recommended by EUCLID and American English, even if both versions are accepted. Whatever my choice, I must ensure that the writing style is consistent.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

The last discussed point is related to chapter eight (8). Even if I used to use track change to modify word documents, this allowed me to understand better the response paper template and how to fill it.

7) CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, the coursepack (period) is very useful. It has allowed me to have a good understanding of exigencies to be respected when I would like to write a paper in American or British English, to avoid plagiarism, and to correct a paper.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Eighth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.